

REARY

Synthesis of Homodiploschistic Acid Methyl Ester

T. R. Seshadri and G. E. V. Subramanian

Atranorin and chloroatranorin, which are often found as mixtures, have been effectively separated by column chromatography on alumina. Their aldehyde groups have been converted into hydroxyl groups by alkaline hydrogen peroxide. This conversion is of interest in the biogenesis of dopsides.

In an earlier paper¹ the synthesis of diploschistic acid (II), a naturally occurring dopside, was reported. This synthesis involved the preparation of the dopside aldehyde (I) as an intermediate which was subjected to oxidation with alkaline hydrogen peroxide. This reaction has now been extended to two more cases, viz., atranorin and chloroatranorin, giving the corresponding hydroxy derivatives. In all these cases the reaction could be carried out without the fission of the dopside linkage. They lend further support to the view of the possible path of biogenesis of the 3-hydroxy compounds, starting from a preformed dopside, as discussed in earlier papers¹⁻³. It was suggested that the 3-aldehyde represented an intermediate stage and it underwent oxidation of the Dakin type. The methyl ester of homodiploschistic acid or its chloro derivative has not so far been found to occur in nature, but their occurrence could be expected on consideration of analogy with similar compounds.

1. Seshadri, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1944, 20A, 1.

2. Seshadri and Venkatasubramanian, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1658.

3. Neelakantan, Padmasini and Seshadri, unpublished results.

4. St. Flu, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1933, 16, 282.

The co-occurrence of atranorin and chloroatranorin in *Evernia prunastri*, which is an abundant source for them, would suggest the formation of chloroatranorin from atranorin. This probability has, in fact, been realised in the laboratory experiments by chlorination of atranorin with calculated amounts of chlorine².

The initial experiments on the oxidation of atranorin were carried out with a natural sample of atranorin of indefinite purity. This sample was obtained from the original preparation of St. Pfau, apparently isolated from *Evernia prunastri*. It was found to be a difficultly separable mixture of atranorin and chloroatranorin. The method of purification described by St. Pfau by repeated crystallisation from chloroform, in which chloroatranorin was sparingly soluble, was laborious and incomplete over a number of stages. The two have now been separated effectively by adsorption chromatography on neutral alumina, employing frontal analysis with chloroform as the mobile phase.

EXPERIMENTAL

The mixture of atranorin and chloroatranorin was purified by adsorption on Brockmann's neutral alumina, washed with 2*N*-HCl and dried at 100°. Chloroform was used as the mobile phase. Atranorin was eluted first, followed by chloroatranorin. These were crystallised from benzene, m.p. 195-96° and 207-208° respectively. Both had the same absorption spectrum in the IR, C=O region; $\nu_{\max}$ 1667 cm^{-1} , 1639 cm^{-1} .

Methyl 5-Chlorohomodiploschistesate (IV).—Chloroatranorin (0.75 g.) was dissolved in aqueous 4% NaOH solution (5ml) and cooled to 10°. A 6% solution of hydrogen peroxide (5ml) was added in lots during 15 mins. The mixture was occasionally shaken and left at 10° for 45 mins. The solution was acidified and the solid separating was filtered and crystallised from benzene-light petroleum (40-60°). The oxidation product was obtained as colorless tablets, m.p. 158-59°. (Found: C, 54.6; H, 4.7. Calc. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_5\text{Cl}$: C, 54.5; H, 4.3%). It developed a blue colour with ethanolic ferric chloride ($\lambda_{\max}$ 310 $\text{m}\mu$, 252 $\text{m}\mu$; $\nu_{\max}$ 1672 cm^{-1} , 1634 cm^{-1}).

The *tetra-acetyl derivative*, prepared by the acetic anhydride-sulphuric acid method, crystallised from methanol as colorless thin plates, m.p. 192°. (Found: C, 55.4; H, 4.8. Calc. for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_{11}\text{Cl}$: C, 55.3; H, 4.4%).

Methyl homodiploschistesate (III) was obtained from atranorin by a similar procedure. It crystallised from benzene-light petroleum (40-60°) as colorless tablets, m.p. 148-49°. (Found: C, 60.2; H, 5.4. Calc. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_8$: C, 59.7, H, 5.0%). It produced a blue colour with ethanolic ferric chloride. ($\lambda_{\max}$ 306, 283, 252 $\text{m}\mu$). The tetra-acetyl derivative, prepared by the acetic anhydride-pyridine method, crystallised from methanol in colorless thin plates, m.p. 166-67°. (Found: C, 58.9; H, 5.6. Calc. for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_{11}$: C, 58.9; H, 4.9%).

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